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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The OIKONET Newsletters were one of the ways of communicating project activities. They were sent to the subscribers and their copy was archived and then made available through the project website. Regular issues published past and upcoming events and activities, and special releases informed readers about the project conferences. They were distributed during the project lifetime at a rate of three per year to a growing subscriber list.

Six regular and three special issues were distributed during the project:

- 1 May 2014: http://www.oikonet.org/public/newsletter/newsletter_1.html
- 2 September 2014: http://www.oikonet.org/public/newsletter/newsletter_2.html
- 3 April 2015: http://www.oikonet.org/public/newsletter/newsletter_3.html
- 4 October 2015: http://www.oikonet.org/public/newsletter/newsletter_4.html
- 5 May 2016: http://www.oikonet.org/public/newsletter/newsletter_5.html
- 6 February 2017: http://www.oikonet.org/public/newsletter/newsletter_6.html

In addition, there were three special issues to promote the three international conferences:

- Barcelona International Conference:
http://www.oikonet.org/public/communications/conference_barcelona.html
- Bratislava International Conference:
http://www.oikonet.org/public/communications/conference_bratislava.html
- Manchester International Conference (updated):
http://www.oikonet.org/public/communications/conference_manchester.html

The MailChimp service was used to deliver newsletters; its statistics show high delivery and opening rates.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose of the newsletters was to increase awareness of interested individuals. Regular issues published past and upcoming events and activities, and special releases were published to inform subscribers of the project conferences. They were distributed during the project lifetime at a rate of 2-3 per year and promoted through a mailing list and the social web of the project. The number of recipients has steadily increased during the project reaching 374 recipients in the latest issues.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The editing, graphic design and newsletter distribution were carried out by LA SALLE, with the collaboration of FASTU. Partners contributed with the contents for the newsletters.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

All the activities carried out in the project which were of interest for a stakeholder group (academics, researchers, professionals, administrations, etc.) have been included in the contents of the newsletter. The newsletters are a complement and a compilation of the information which has been posted in the web portal and in the social media channels.

3 REGULAR ISSUES

OIKONET Newsletters were an email-based dissemination tool with standardized layout and information structure. They were published twice a year, usually in March and September, and they informed about the project activities, about past and upcoming events. They were sent to the subscribers and their copy is archived and available through the OIKONET website. Newsletters were aimed specifically toward project partners and of academic or non-academic stakeholders interested in project activities, but the subscription was open to the general public too. Full text of all newsletters is in the Appendix A.

The newsletters were distributed using the MailChimp service to avoid blocking of bulk mail by spam filters. Subscription management was done through this service too.

3.1 OIKONET Newsletter #01

[The first OIKONET Newsletter](#) issue was published on March 11, 2014. It informed about the project start, about its areas of activity and about upcoming events. There is also information on the project learning activities, on community engagement and on prepared meetings. The newsletter informs about the project website, about the prepared Lisbon workshop and about the first network conference.

This first newsletter had 70 subscribers and its opening rate was 58%, well over the industry average. Click rate was 13%.

Welcome to the first newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union.

The objective of OIKONET is to create a platform of collaboration to study contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social.

OIKONET will intertwine three areas of activity:

1. Research on housing studies from a multidisciplinary and global approach;
2. Participatory actions to engage communities in the definition, solution and evaluation of housing problems; and
3. Pedagogical activities which bring together different stakeholders, learning environments and disciplines.

Figure 1. Screenshot of OIKONET Newsletter #01 in a web browser.

3.2 OIKONET Newsletter #02

[OIKONET Newsletter #2](#) was published on September 10, 2014. Its main topic was the updated information on the prepared Barcelona conference. Detailed description of the main event of the summer – the Lisbon workshop – was included too, as well as mentioning the sub-network meetings. The newsletter promoted the social web of the project (Facebook, Google+, Twitter and YouTube) and the first release of [OIKONETWORK](#) (the visual map enabling users to navigate through the network of information generated by OIKONET partners during the project).

This newsletter issue already had 193 subscribers, the opening rate was 50%, and click rate was 16%.

Welcome to the second newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union. The project has been running for almost one year, and some of the outputs start to be visible in the project website.

OIKONET is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions, and pedagogical and research activities bring together multiple stakeholders and disciplines, in Europe and around the world.

The most important upcoming event is the first OIKONET International Conference in Barcelona, on 25th and 26th September. The most relevant event carried out in the previous months has been the first OIKONET International Workshop in Lisbon. Please see below for a more detailed information on these events.

The OIKONET Team.

● Barcelona conference

The first [OIKONET International Conference](#) will take place at the School of Architecture La Salle, in Barcelona, on September 25th and 26th, 2014.

A poster exhibition is open to all the participants. The deadline to receive the final version of the paper (in A0 format) is September 12th, 2014. The participation in this conference is free of charge. If you are interested to attend, please write us to info@oikonet

Upcoming events

September 25-26, 2014. First international OIKONET conference, hosted by the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona.

December 12, 2014. The third meeting of the Subnetwork "Housing Research" will take place on December 12th 2014 in Budapest, organized by Eötvös

Figure 2. Screenshot of OIKONET Newsletter #02 in a web browser.

3.3 OIKONET Newsletter #03

[Third OIKONET Newsletter issue](#) was published on April 28, 2015. It had 207 subscribers and 52% opening rate. The main topics of this issue were the second international conference “Global Dwelling” and preparation of the second OIKONET international workshop “Growth/Shrinkage” which will take place in Cottbus. The newsletter informs about the conference papers already published or prepared for the summer events, about the active learning spaces of the project and about the sub-network meetings (Budapest, Istanbul, and Bratislava). Upgrade of the OIKONET web portal was mentioned too.

[View it in your browser](#)

NEWSLETTER

// April 2015

#03

Welcome to the third newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union. This project is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions and pedagogical and research activities bring together various stakeholders and multiple disciplines.

The most relevant upcoming events are the international workshop in Cottbus in June and the second network conference on Global Dwelling in Bratislava, in September. Results of the project are being presented in international on pedagogic innovation and housing studies. Five learning spaces have been collaboratively designed and implemented by partners during the Winter semester, and some of them continue being active in the Spring semester. The third round of subnetwork meetings took place between December and February. The OIKONET web portal has been upgraded with new environments which facilitate access to the activities and outcomes of the project.

The OIKONET Team.

● Second international conference: “Global Dwelling”

The second OIKONET International Conference will take place at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, in Bratislava, on September 24-25th, 2015.

The OIKONET conferences on Global Dwelling started last year with the [first conference in Barcelona](#). The second conference will focus on housing regeneration strategies as mechanisms to improve the existing living conditions in the

Upcoming events

June 1-6, 2015. Second international OIKONET workshop “Growth/Shrinkage”, hosted by the Brandenburg University of Technology, Cottbus, Germany. Students from schools which are not OIKONET members can join the workshop with their own funding. If you are interested, please contact us at

Figure 3. Screenshot of OIKONET Newsletter #03 in a web browser.

3.4 OIKONET Newsletter #04

[Fourth OIKONET Newsletter issue](#) was published on October 26, 2015. It had 265 subscribers and 43% opening rate. This newsletter informed about the Bratislava conference, the Cottbus workshop “Growth / Shrinkage” and the running first edition of the MOOC “Housing Design: From Concept to Fabrication”. Other topics of this issue were information on the new workspaces, participation workshop in Skopje, and the start of the “Thinking dwelling” programme. Upcoming events, subnetwork meetings and social web links were also mentioned.

[View it in your browser](#)

NEWSLETTER

// October 2015

#04

Welcome to the fourth newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union. OIKONET is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions, and pedagogical and research activities bring together multiple stakeholders and disciplines. A total of 34 organizations – including schools of architecture and planning, research groups, professional organizations and local administrations – representing 29 countries – 4 of them outside Europe – are participating in this network.

The most important events carried out since our last April newsletter have been the second OIKONET international conference “Global Dwelling” in Bratislava, Slovakia, and the second international workshop in Cottbus, Germany.

The OIKONET Team.

● Bratislava conference

The second international OIKONET conference on “Global Dwelling” took place at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, in Slovakia, on September 25th. The conference focused on regeneration strategies as mechanisms that are applied to improve the existing living conditions in urban areas around the world. Eleven papers were presented and twenty-two posters exhibited. The conference ended with a panel discussion with the participation of Prof. Flora Samuel, University of Sheffield, United Kingdom; Prof. Richard Hayward, from University of Greenwich, United Kingdom; and Prof. Aseem Inam, from University of Toronto, Canada.

Upcoming events

November 20, 2015. The fifth meeting of the group Housing Research will take place in the premises of Faculty of Law of the University of Zagreb.

December 18, 2015. The Community Participation group will have the fifth meeting at the Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, in Skopje.

January 22, 2016. The fifth meeting of the Pedagogical

Figure 4. Screenshot of OIKONET Newsletter #04 in a web browser.

3.5 OIKONET Newsletter #05

[Fifth OIKONET Newsletter issue](#) was published on May 05, 2016. It had 312 subscribers and 41% opening rate. It invited to the third international conference “Global Dwelling” in Manchester, to the third OIKONET International Workshop “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating liveable cities” and to the second edition of the MOOC “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication”. This issue also presented the OIKONET Reader #2, informed about conference papers and journal articles and about the current learning spaces. The Facebook page progress, YouTube channel update and web portal upgrade were mentioned too. Additional information on subnetwork meetings, upcoming events, current exhibitions and participatory actions was provided too.

[View it in your browser](#)

NEWSLETTER

// May 2016

#05

Welcome to the fifth regular newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union, 2013-2016. This project is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions and pedagogical and research activities bring together various stakeholders and multiple disciplines. Thirty four partners in Europe and around the world participate on the activities of the project, which is approaching its final phase.

The most relevant upcoming events are the third international workshop in Belgrade in June and the third conference on “Global Dwelling”, which will take place in Manchester in September 2016 hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire. The second run of the MOOC “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication” started on May.

The OIKONET Team.

● Third OIKONET International Conference: “Global Dwelling: Sustainability-Design-Participation”

The OIKONET conferences on “Global Dwelling” started in 2014 with the first conference at the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain. A year later, a second conference was held at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology.

The third conference will take place at the Renaissance Hotel, Manchester, UK, on 23 September 2016. A call for

Upcoming events

June 6-11, 2016. Third international OIKONET workshop “Renewing / Revitalizing”, Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from 6th to 11th of June 2016. This workshop will be dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. Students from schools that are not

Figure 5. Screenshot of OIKONET Newsletter #05 in a web browser.

3.6 OIKONET Newsletter #06

[Sixth OIKONET Newsletter issue](#) was published on February 28, 2017. It was the final issue, prepared just before the end of the project. It had 363 subscribers and 33% opening rate. The main topics of this issue were the resume of the third international conference “Global Dwelling” in Manchester and of the third OIKONET international workshop in Belgrade, information on the second edition of the MOOC “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication” and on the OIKOPEDIA upgrade. Start of a series of postgraduate workshops was announced. Next paragraphs were about the new learning spaces and about current conference papers and articles. Additional information on upcoming events and current participatory actions, exhibitions, YouTube channel updates and Facebook link were provided too.

[View it in your browser](#)

NEWSLETTER

// February 2017

#06

Welcome to the sixth and final newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union, 2013-2016. This project has created a collaborative platform to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions and pedagogical and research activities have brought together various stakeholders and multiple disciplines. Thirty-four partners in twenty-five countries in Europe and around the world have participated in the project activities.

The most relevant actions in the last period of the project have been the third international conference on “Global Dwelling”, held in Manchester in September 2016, and the third international workshop hosted by the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, in June 2016. The second edition of the OIKONET MOOC “Housing Design” took place in May/June 2016. In the first semester of the academic year 2016/17, the activity around the collaborative learning spaces continued with the second edition of “Thinking Dwelling” and “Urban Systems”. In recent months, partners have been active in the dissemination of the project outcomes in international conferences such as the ENHR in Belfast and the DOCOMOMO in Lisbon.

The project activities carried out with EU support finished on 31st December 2016. Afterwards, the reports of the work were prepared and they will be released to the public in the coming weeks through the project website. The last output of the project is a book which summarizes the work done by the network during the three-years of activity. This book will be available both in printed and on-line versions in May 2017.

Even though the funding period has ended, the project activities continue. During the second semester of 2016/17, there are two learning spaces active in OIKODOMOS Workspaces: a new learning space “Danube Urban and Cultural Studies”, led by the Faculty of Architecture of Slovak Technical University and the sixth edition of “Introduction to Housing”, led by the School of Architecture of Valencia. Lastly, the program of the first OIKONET Postgraduate Workshop to take place in June 2017 at the School of Architecture in Valencia will be announced soon.

The OIKONET Team.

Figure 6. Screenshot of OIKONET Newsletter #06 in a web browser.

4 SPECIAL ISSUES

The OIKONET newsletter infrastructure (layout, subscriber list, mailing service) was used also for promotion of the network conferences Global Dwelling in Barcelona and Bratislava.

4.1 First International Conference Global Dwelling

The newsletter promoting the first OIKONET conference (in Barcelona on September 25-26, 2014) was published on June 02, 2014. It included links to the regularly updated conference blog, call for papers and characteristics of the keynote speakers.

This newsletter had 70 subscribers, its opening rate was 70% (industry average is 16%), and its click rate was 19%.

[View it in your browser](#)

GLOBAL DWELLING | 25-26 September 2014

School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

This conference will address the global dimension of contemporary housing as manifested in the demands for citizens' participation, social inclusiveness, adaptability and sustainability of the built environment and fostering a sense of belonging. Even though the specific answers to these demands differ in each society the underlying forces that support them have a global dimension. An appropriate answer will not derive exclusively from the solutions that professionals – architects, urban planners – can provide based on their established body of knowledge. Rather, it is necessary to confront those demands in an open manner, investigating the nature of the problem in collaboration with all stakeholders involved, in order to find the appropriate answer to the challenges that dwelling raises today.

Therefore, the conference will bring together representatives of academic institutions, research organizations, community groups and local authorities, with the purpose to fostering a common view of what housing means today, at a global scale.

OPEN CALL FOR POSTERS: A poster exhibition is included in the programme. If you would like to present a poster, please contact us. The deadline to receive the final version of the paper (in A0 format) is July 31, 2014.

Please see the [CONFERENCE PROGRAM](#) and [POSTER](#)

Figure 7. Screenshot of the first OIKONET Campaign newsletter in a web browser.

4.2 Second International Conference Global Dwelling

Announcement of the second OIKONET conference (in Bratislava on September 25, 2015, focusing on the housing regeneration strategies) was published on March 06, 2015. It included a call for papers, link to the conference blog, and characteristics of the keynote speakers.

This newsletter had 192 subscribers, its opening rate was 63%, well over the industry average. The click rate was 10%.

Second International Conference GLOBAL DWELLING Housing regeneration strategies Bratislava, 25 September 2015

The second [OIKONET](#) conference on the topic **Global Dwelling** will focus on regeneration strategies as mechanisms that are applied to improve the existing living conditions in urban areas around the world. Nowadays, various local and global factors cause the appearance of disadvantaged communities and declining urban areas worldwide. Instead of offering universal solutions, contemporary integrated interventions are intended to tackle specific problems by encompassing social, economic and urban dimensions. By building on existing local forces – involving all stakeholders and the local community in the process of finding solutions–, urban areas can unleash their endogenous regeneration potential. Even though being deeply influenced by local conditions, this process acquires a global dimension when certain mechanisms and policies – such as planned gentrification and social mix – are reproduced at multiple locations and cultures.

The conference will discuss the implications of such integrated approaches based on the design and implementation of strategies for the regeneration of communities – at a social, economic and environmental level. We invite researchers, lecturers, design studio instructors, policy makers, practitioners and community leaders, involved in the research, design and implementation of housing regeneration strategies, to submit original papers addressing the following issues:

- What are the consequences – for architecture and urban planning education – of designing regeneration strategies instead of designing housing developments?
- How are the visions and goals in a community renewal process, collectively defined?
- Which urban regeneration strategies are needed to achieve a sustainable urban development (at the cultural, economic, social and environmental level)?

Figure 8. Screenshot of the second OIKONET Campaign newsletter in a web browser.

4.3 Third International Conference Global Dwelling

Announcement of the third OIKONET conference (in Manchester on September 23, 2016, focusing on the housing regeneration strategies) was published on December 16, 2015. It included a call for papers, link to the conference blog, and characteristics of the keynote speakers. This newsletter had 262 subscribers and its opening rate was 44%.

Third International Conference GLOBAL DWELLING Sustainability - Design - Participation Manchester, 23 September 2016

The [third OIKONET conference on 'Global Dwelling'](#) will be hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire. OIKONET is a European project co-funded by the Executive Agency of Education, Audiovisual and Culture (EACEA) with the purpose of studying contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social.

The [first OIKONET conference](#) was organized by La Salle School of Architecture in Barcelona, Spain, in September 2014; [the second one](#) by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, in September 2015. This third conference will showcase the results obtained in the three years of activity of OIKONET intertwining research, pedagogy and community participation around the topic 'Global Dwelling'. During this period OIKONET partners have been involved in the design and implementation of pedagogic and research activities which have brought together schools of architecture and planning, research groups, professional organizations and local administrations. This is reflected in the collaborative learning spaces and workshops, community-based projects and participatory actions carried out with the participation of architecture students, lecturers, researchers and citizens.

The conference program will be structure in three themes:

1. **Sustainability of housing environments.** The problem of sustainability has been widely recognised as a priority by governments, civil society and businesses across the world. The built environment is a key component of a sustainable development, and the need for sustainable housing environments and communities cannot be overemphasised given the increasing demand for waste minimisation, sustainable transport and renewable energy.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the third OIKONET Campaign newsletter in a web browser.

4.4 Third International Conference (update)

Update of the third OIKONET conference announcement was published on February 04, 2015. It had 263 subscribers and its opening rate was 43%. This update was almost identical with the previous issue; it was a reminder of the call for papers.

OIKONET

A GLOBAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY NETWORK ON HOUSING RESEARCH AND LEARNING

Third International Conference GLOBAL DWELLING Sustainability - Design - Participation Manchester, 23 September 2016

The deadline to submit abstracts to the [Third OIKONET "Global Dwelling" Conference](#) is approaching. You can send us your proposals until **15 February 2016**. Accepted papers will be published in Volume Number 173 in [WIT Transactions on The Built Environment](#). Papers will be peer reviewed by at least two members of the Scientific Committee. We are looking forward to receiving your abstracts and meeting you in September in Manchester!

The [third OIKONET conference on 'Global Dwelling'](#) will be hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire. [OIKONET](#) is a European project co-funded by the Executive Agency of Education, Audiovisual and Culture (EACEA) with the purpose of studying contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social.

The [first OIKONET conference](#) was organized by La Salle School of Architecture in Barcelona, Spain, in September 2014; [the second one](#) by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, in September 2015. This third conference will showcase the results obtained in the three years of activity of OIKONET intertwining research, pedagogy and community participation around the topic 'Global Dwelling'. During this period OIKONET partners have been involved in the design and implementation of pedagogic and research activities which have brought together schools of architecture and planning, research groups, professional organizations and local administrations. This is reflected in the collaborative learning spaces and workshops, community-based projects and participatory actions carried out with the participation of

Figure 10. Screenshot of the updated third OIKONET Campaign newsletter in a web browser.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The regular OIKONET newsletters were published as planned in the project proposal (six issues – for their content see Appendix A), and three special issues to promote the three network conferences. The subscriber list grew from the initial 70 to 374 in the latest distributions.

The Newsletter has been an important dissemination tool especially in the later stages of the project, when the list of subscribers included a number of recipients outside the project consortium. After the project completion the newsletter archive remains accessible on the OIKONET web portal (see Appendix C) and offers useful information on the history of project activities, including relevant links. It is still possible to publish additional issues announcing project-related activities after the funding period (e.g. OIKONET book accessibility, post-graduate workshops, opening of project-based learning spaces, new MOOC editions).

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A. Newsletter Content

Here we append the full text of the published OIKONET newsletters. As they cannot be converted from the html format of emails to the docx format of this report without layout changes, we insert here only the text of the newsletters. For exact layout of these newsletter issues look on the archived versions on the project website (links are in the appendix C).

A.1 OIKONET Newsletter #01

NEWSLETTER // March 2014

Welcome to the first newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union.

The objective of OIKONET is to create a platform of collaboration to study contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social.

OIKONET will intertwine three areas of activity:

1. Research on housing studies from a multidisciplinary and global approach;
2. Participatory actions to engage communities in the definition, solution and evaluation of housing problems; and
3. Pedagogical activities which bring together different stakeholders, learning environments and disciplines.

Thirty-four organizations in Europe and around the world participate in the three year of project, including universities, research organizations, local administrations, professional, and social organizations.

The project activities started in October 2013 and will last three years. We hope that these activities are of your interest and, eventually, to count on your participation in some of them.

Leandro Madrazo, OIKONET Project Coordinator

Learning activities

During the Winter semester 2013-14, a “Research Seminar on Contemporary Housing” took place at the School of Architecture La Salle about the theme of “Civic Housing”. The purpose of the seminar was to develop strategies to foster the participation of dwellers in the design, use and transformation of housing. In February 2014, the learning space “Introduction to housing” has initiated. The purpose of this learning space –coordinated by the School of Architecture of Valencia, Spain– is to introduce first year students to the fundamentals of architecture through the design of a house. More learning spaces are being planned with the participation of the schools of architecture that are now part of OIKONET.

Community engagement

From October 2013 to January 2014, the School of Architecture La Salle and Sostre Cívica have been collaborating in a co-housing project in the Born, a neighbourhood in Barcelona. Architecture students and members of the cooperative have been involved in a process of analysis and reflection about the characteristics of the future dwellings. From 10th to 15th of March, a workshop took place in the municipality of Ilinden, Macedonia, with the participation

of students and teachers from the Faculty of Architecture (UKIM) and of local residents. New pedagogic activities with the collaboration of citizens, local authorities and universities will take place in Bratislava (Slovakia) and Rimini (Italy) during the coming months.

Meetings

Between December 2013 and February 2014, the first OIKONET meetings of the three subnetworks took place in Preston, UK (Research, hosted by UCLan); and in Barcelona, Spain (Pedagogy and Community, hosted by La Salle School of Architecture). The specific goals for each subnetwork are summarized in the presentations available on the web portal.

Web portal

The OIKONET portal is already operative. It contains information about the activities carried out in the project, profile of the partners and coming events. The portal provides access to the OIKONET communities on Google Plus and Facebook.

Lisbon Workshop

An international workshop dedicated to study contemporary patterns in mass housing will take place in Lisbon, from 14th to 19th July 2014. The workshop is organized by ISCTE, an OIKONET partner. Around 40 students from 13 schools of architecture and urban planning will take part in it. Before the meeting in Lisbon, preparatory works will be carried out by the students that participate in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus. If you are interested in joining the workshop, please contact us.

International Conference

The first OIKONET international conference will be hosted by the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, 25th and 26th September 2014. Representatives of the 34 institutions participating in OIKONET will attend this conference. The program will be structured in three blocks, each one dedicated to the three subareas of the network: housing research, community participation and pedagogic innovation in housing studies. Two keynote speakers will address the themes of the conference.

Upcoming events

June 16-17, 2014. The second meeting of the subnetwork Research will take place at the University of Ljubljana.

June 26-27, 2014. The second meeting of the subnetwork Community will be take place in Rimini, Italy, organized by the Chamber of Architects and by Heriscape.

July 14-19, 2014. International Workshop “Contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe”, organized by ISCTE Lisbon.

September 25-26, 2014. First international OIKONET conference, hosted by the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona.

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A.2 OIKONET Newsletter #02

NEWSLETTER// September 2014

Welcome to the second newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong

Learning Programme of the European Union. The project has been running for almost one year, and some of the outputs start to be visible in the project website.

OIKONET is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions, and pedagogical and research activities bring together multiple stakeholders and disciplines, in Europe and around the world.

The most important upcoming event is the first OIKONET International Conference in Barcelona, on 25th and 26th September. The most relevant event carried out in the previous months has been the first OIKONET International Workshop in Lisbon. Please see below for a more detailed information on these events.

The OIKONET Team.

Barcelona conference

The first OIKONET International Conference will take place at the School of Architecture La Salle, in Barcelona, on September 25th and 26th, 2014.

A poster exhibition is open to all the participants. The deadline to receive the final version of the paper (in A0 format) is September 12th, 2014. The participation in this conference is free of charge. If you are interested to attend, please write us to info@oikonet

The conference theme –Global Dwelling– will encompass issues such as citizens' participation and social inclusiveness, adaptability and sustainability of the built environment, community building and housing policies. The conference will bring together representatives of academic institutions, research organizations, community groups and local authorities.

The program includes 19 presentations of representatives coming from 25 countries worldwide which will address the following topics: changing meanings of home, housing policies, energy efficiency in housing, social sustainability, affordable housing, community participation, housing design education, sustainable housing, and urban renewal.

Two keynote speeches will be delivered by Claire Lévy-Vroelant, Professor of Sociology, Université de Paris-8 Saint-Denis, France, and Ekim Tan, founder of Play the City Studio.

A poster exhibition is open to all the participants. The deadline to receive the final version of the paper (in A0 format) is September 12th, 2014. The participation in this conference is free of charge. If you are interested to attend, please write us to info@oikonet.org

Lisbon workshop

The first OIKONET International Workshop ran from 14th to 19th July 2014 in Lisbon at ISCTE-IUL, with the collaboration of two associated research centres - ISTAR-IUL and DINÂMIA'CET-IUL – and of the digital fabrication laboratory Vitruvius FABLAB-IUL.

The objective of this six-day workshop was to develop a cross-disciplinary dialogue aimed at identifying the meanings and forms of contemporary living patterns in mass housing in Europe, by opposing “formal” and “informal” housing. Mass housing in Europe – “formal” housing– has been studied for a long period, because it has been a solution to democratize the access to dwelling for a large number of people. In its origins, mass housing represented an innovative solution to respond to the housing needs of the population. In the last decades, however, mass housing programs fell into disrepute and began to decline. This type of housing became a place associated with uniformity, repetition, anonymity and uprooting. On the other hand, “informal” mass housing – self-built housing – brings about more diversity and a bigger sense of

appropriation and identification of the dwellers with their living place.

The work carried out in the workshop focused on two neighbourhoods in Lisbon: one, representative of formal mass housing - “Portela de Sacavém” and, another one - “Bairro da Liberdade” which is typical of informal mass housing. The “Portela de Sacavém” (1965-1978) mass housing plan created by Fernando Silva (1914-1983) became a model of how to intervene in the urban periphery. The “Bairro da Liberdade” (1969-80) is an informal settlement. Dwellings were built for the proletariat and landowners sought to minimize construction costs and optimize land value. These two places offered the opportunity to rethink the contemporary living patterns in mass housing design. Today, we should look at these forms of housing – formal and informal – in order to understand the way people live.

The overall housing design process was addressed during the activities, starting from participation and ending with fabrication. The teaching methodology was based on a combination of lectures, field studies, and design studio work.

About 50 students from 15 European Schools of Architecture discussed, designed, fabricated and assembled a full-scale prototype of a modular housing system. 25 teachers from OIKONET organizations participated actively in the formulation of design strategies, the project critiques and fabrication process.

More information can be found at the blog of the Lisbon Workshop. A special radio report dedicated to the workshop was produced by UK-based design magazine MONOCLE.

Meetings

The members of the Subnetwork “Pedagogical Activities” met in July with occasion of the workshop in Lisbon. This was the second meeting of the group since the start of the project. During three days, faculty members from the participating schools discussed the strategies to design and implement learning activities collaboratively. In the coming academic year, OIKONET partner schools will jointly carry out learning activities on the following themes: “Introduction to Housing”, “Housing Systems”, “Threshold Matters” and “Housing Regeneration Strategies”.

The second meeting of the Subnetwork "Housing Research" took place in June at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia, hosted by Prof. Sašo Medved. Twelve participants representing nine partner institutions participated in the meeting. The group discussed the on-going work carried out by the subnetwork: the position papers describing the research conducted by partners about housing; the Oikopedia entries; and the table summarizing the research topics that the network is concerned with. A working session was dedicated to discuss the structure of the research topics, and the relationships with the other two subnetworks (Community Participation, Pedagogy).

The Subnetwork "Community Participation" also met for the second time in June. The meeting was organised by Heriscape and the Ordine Architetti Paesaggisti Pianificatori e Conservatori della Provincia di Rimini. Representatives from the municipality and social organizations presented their strategies and actions to provide housing to the population that cannot afford it. Public-private collaborations, to provide solutions to social housing shortage, were discussed during the meeting. A participatory action will be designed in the context of this subnetwork to analyse the difficulties that young people have to have access to a home in Rimini. Partners discussed strategies to exchange their experiences and to join efforts in the participatory actions to be developed in the project with the objective of involving citizens in the decision making processes which concern their habitat.

Video of participatory actions

A video summarizing the pedagogic experience carried out within the seminar "Civic Housing" at the School of Architecture La Salle during the Fall semester 2013_14 has been produced. Students from the School of Architecture La Salle and members of the association Sostre Cívic in Barcelona participated in a process aimed at involving dwellers in the process of designing their future homes. This video describes the learning design process which involved both, students and dwellers.

OIKONETWORK

The first release of OIKONETWORK has been launched. This visual map enables users to navigate through the network of information generated by OIKONET partners during the project.

OIKONET in the social web

Facebook site of OIKONET project has been here for some time - we will make it more living and attractive now. We will create special Facebook Groups to support the learning activities carried out by the different participating schools. Feel free to join us on Facebook. Also, you can find information about the activities of the project members in OIKONET Google Plus Community. On OIKONET YouTube channel you can find the videos produced in the project. And you can follow us on Twitter.

Upcoming events

September 25-26, 2014. First international OIKONET conference, hosted by the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona.

December 12, 2014. The third meeting of the Subnetwork "Housing Research" will take place on December 12th 2014 in Budapest, organized by Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE).

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A.3 OIKONET Newsletter #03

NEWSLETTER// April 2015

Welcome to the third newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union. This project is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions and pedagogical and research activities bring together various stakeholders and multiple disciplines.

The most relevant upcoming events are the international workshop in Cottbus in June and the second network conference on Global Dwelling in Bratislava, in September. Results of the project are being presented in international on pedagogic innovation and housing studies. Five learning spaces have been collaboratively designed and implemented by partners during the Winter semester, and some of them continue being active in the Spring semester. The third round of subnetwork meetings took place between December and February. The OIKONET web portal has been upgraded with new environments which facilitate access to the activities and outcomes of the project.

The OIKONET Team.

Second international conference: “Global Dwelling”

The second OIKONET International Conference will take place at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, in Bratislava, on September 24-25th, 2015.

The OIKONET conferences on Global Dwelling started last year with the first conference in Barcelona. The second conference will focus on housing regeneration strategies as mechanisms to improve the existing living conditions in the urban areas around the world. Keynote speeches will be delivered by Becky Tunstam, Professor of Housing Policy at the University of York, UK, and Aseem Inam, Associate Professor of Urbanism at Parsons The New School for Design in New York City, US.

A call for papers and posters will remain open until May 15th. Abstracts will be evaluated by the Scientific Committee members. Up to 12 selected papers will be presented at the conference and published in the proceedings. Abstracts that are not selected will have the opportunity to be presented in the poster session. If you need more information, please write us to info@oikonet.org. A registration form is already available.

The opening of the poster section will take place on Thursday, September 24th, in the evening; Friday 25th will be dedicated to paper presentations and keynote speeches.

Second international workshop: “Growth / Shrinkage”

The second OIKONET International Workshop will take place at Cottbus on June 1-6, 2015, hosted by the Brandenburg University of Technology. This workshop will explore the complementarities of growing and shrinking, two urban development patterns exemplified by the cities of Berlin and Cottbus, respectively. Growth usually suggests development and wealth, but this trend presents also a number of urban challenges: How can a city deal with growth in order to maintain adequate living standards and infrastructural supply for its inhabitants? Shrinkage often stands for decline and decay, but it could also be seen as an opportunity for urban renewal. What are then the opportunities of shrinkage and how can a place be downsized without being destroyed?

The workshop will focus on two cities representing the two sides of the same coin: Berlin, the German capital, with a growing number of inhabitants, with a housing shortage that attracts global investors; and Cottbus, a former industrial city in Eastern Germany, facing a decline of population and economic stagnation.

Around fifty students and twenty-five faculty members from the fifteen schools of architecture and urban planning members of OIKONET are expected to participate. Yet, participation is open to students from other schools providing they have their own funding. If you would like to join the workshop, please contact us at info@oikonet.org.

Conference Papers

A paper describing the work about pedagogic innovation carried out in OIKONET was presented by Leandro Madrazo at the 7th International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation (ICERI), held in Seville (Spain), on the 17th, 18th and 19th of November, 2014.

A paper about the research and pedagogic activities carried out in OIKONET around the theme urban regeneration was presented by Karim Hadjri at the conference that took place at the University of Liverpool, 8th and 9th April 2015. The paper was co-authored by Gábor Csanádi, Adrienne Csizmady, Gergely Olt, Mirjana Devetakovic, Tatjana Mrdjenovic, Viera Joklova, Leandro Madrazo, Elina Krasilnikova and Larisa Kuzina. The presentation took place on the 8th of April during the first session on Housing and Urbanism. The session was well attended

with a very positive response to the presented papers leading to a lively and interesting debate. Some questions were raised about the OIKONET presentation concerning the tools and methods used to engage stakeholders in the pedagogic activities.

Some more conference papers documenting the achievements of OIKONET project are under way. There are some already accepted abstracts: “IPI Methodology In Habitat Regeneration Strategies Using OIKONET Platform” (Changing Cities 2; June 22-26 2015 Porto Heli, Greece; by Tatjana Mrdjenovic, Mirjana Devetaković, Viera Joklova and Elina Krasilnikova); “Innovation in Architectural Education – OIKONET Experience” (4th World Conference on Technology and Engineering Education; September 2-5 2015 Bratislava, Slovakia; by Viera Joklová and Henrich Pifko); “Collaborative web-based learning spaces: Introduction to Housing” (HEAd'15 - 1st International Conference on Higher Education Advances; June 24-26 2015, Valencia, Spain; Nadia Charalambous and Carla Sentieri); “Designing and implementing a collaborative learning space to introduce students to housing” (EDULEARN15, the 7th annual International Conference on Education and New Learning Technologies; July 6-8 2015 Barcelona, Spain; by Carla Sentieri, Nadia Charalambous and Leandro Madrazo).

Learning Spaces

During the Winter semester 2014/15, five learning spaces designed by OIKONET partners, collaboratively, have been implemented. Each learning space has been dedicated to a theme thus enabling different approaches concerning contemporary housing at a global scale:

“Introduction to Housing” introduces first and second year students to some fundamentals of housing design and architecture, led by School of Architecture of Valencia.

“Habitat Regeneration Strategies”, focuses on the redevelopment of deprived areas at various scales (housing, neighbourhood, city, metropolitan area) encompassing multiple aspects of city life: physical, social, economic and environmental. It is led by the University of Belgrade and by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology.

“Threshold Matters” is dedicated to study the intersection of public and domestic spaces. It is led by KU Leuven.

“Housing Systems”, dedicated to the study of the concept of housing system, from design to construction, led by the School of Architecture La Salle.

These learning spaces continue active during the Spring semester. Besides, a new edition of the learning space “Contemporary living patterns” has started. It is dedicated the preparatory activities for the Cottbus workshop and it is coordinated by Université Pierre Mendès-France, from Grenoble.

Subnetwork Meetings

Since the publication of the second issue of the OIKONET Newsletter, there has been a new round of subnetwork meetings.

The third meeting of the subnetwork “Housing Research” took place in Budapest on December 12, 2014, hosted by the Faculty of Social Sciences of the Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE). The discussions during the meeting focused on two topics: habitat regeneration strategies and global dwelling. The first topic is also part of the learning activities carried out by partners of the subnetwork “Pedagogical Activities”, who participated in this meeting to foster the interconnectivity between research and pedagogic activities within the network.

On January 30, 2015, the Department of Architecture of Istanbul Technical University hosted the third meeting of the subnetwork “Pedagogical Activities”. Representatives of 14 architecture and planning schools - members of the OIKONET network - participated in this

meeting, along with pedagogy designers and evaluation experts.

The city of Bratislava hosted the third meeting of the subnetwork “Community Participation” which took place at ARCHA - Centre for Architecture and Urbanism on February 27, 2015. The meeting was dedicated to discuss the on-going participatory activity in Rimini, and to introduce the project to be carried out in the Bratislava Petržalka district. The purpose of this project is to engage citizens in the Central Development Axis of Petržalka. Eight OIKONET partners participated in this encounter.

The next round of subnetwork meetings will take place in June: the Housing Research group will meet in Rotterdam, hosted by the Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies; members of the Pedagogical Activities group will meet in the Brandenburg Technical University in Cottbus with occasion of the second international workshop, and the Community Participation group will gather in Tirana, at the premises of POLIS University.

Upgrade of the OIKONET web portal

An upgrade of the website www.oikonet.org has been recently completed. It includes a new environment –OIKONETWORK– to visualize the relationships about the activities and outcomes produced during the project. The interrelated information that is shown in the visual graph in OIKONETWORK is displayed in the dashboard in the home page. This information system –developed with semantic technologies– has been created for the project of OIKONET by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle.

Upcoming events

June 1-6, 2015. Second international OIKONET workshop “Growth/Shrinkage), hosted by the Brandenburg University of Technology, Cottbus, Germany. Students from schools which are not OIKONET members can join the workshop with their own funding. If you are interested, please contact us at info@oikonet.org.

June 5, 2015. The fourth meeting of the subnetwork Housing Research will take place at the Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies in Rotterdam.

June 9, 2015. The fourth meeting of the subnetwork Community Participation will take place in Tirana hosted by POLIS University.

September 24-25, 2015. The second OIKONET International Conference will take place at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, in Bratislava, on September 24-25th, 2015. Abstracts can be submitted until May 15th. Registration is open.

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A.4 OIKONET Newsletter #04

NEWSLETTER// October 2015

Welcome to the fourth newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union. OIKONET is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today’s societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions, and pedagogical and research activities bring together multiple stakeholders and disciplines. A total of 34 organizations –including schools of architecture and planning, research

groups, professional organizations and local administrations– representing 29 countries – 4 of them outside Europe– are participating in this network.

The most important events carried out since our last April newsletter have been the second OIKONET international conference “Global Dwelling” in Bratislava, Slovakia, and the second international workshop in Cottbus, Germany.

The OIKONET Team.

Bratislava conference

The second international OIKONET conference on “Global Dwelling” took place at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, in Slovakia, on September 25th. The conference focused on regeneration strategies as mechanisms that are applied to improve the existing living conditions in urban areas around the world. Eleven papers were presented and twenty-two posters exhibited. The conference ended with a panel discussion with the participation of Prof. Flora Samuel, University of Sheffield, United Kingdom; Prof. Richard Hayward, from University of Greenwich, United Kingdom; and Prof. Aseem Inam, from University of Toronto, Canada.

Details on the conference program can be found on the conference blog. Recordings of the presentations will be published on the OIKONET YouTube channel and the papers will be available in the proceedings that will be published on the project web portal.

Cottbus workshop: “Growth / Shrinkage”

The second OIKONET International Workshop ran from 1st to 6th June 2015. It was hosted by the Brandenburg Technical University, Cottbus, Germany. The purpose of the workshop was to explore the complementarity of Growing and Shrinking - two urban development patterns exemplified by the cities of Berlin and Cottbus. Using these two cities as case studies, the workshop aimed at exploring urban and architectural scenarios facing increasing and decreasing urban density. Its program included lectures, design studio work and site visits to the areas of study. Preparatory learning activities were carried out by participants prior to the meeting in Cottbus. Around fifty students and twenty-five faculty members from sixteen schools of architecture and urban planning, members of OIKONET, participated in this workshop. The outcomes can be found on the Cottbus workshop blog. Additional information can be found on the OIKONET Facebook page.

THINKING DWELLING program

In September 2015, the program THINKING DWELLING has started at the School of Architecture La Salle. The objective of this program is to encourage students and teachers of architecture to reflect about the forms of living in the contemporary world, and to develop a critical understanding about the role of the architect in the process of defining the spaces we inhabit. Students and teachers, from the institutions that are part of OIKONET, were invited to participate, sending their contributions to the three proposed activities: Representing, Experiencing and Projecting. The outcomes have been collected in a publication.

OIKONET MOOC

The OIKONET MOOC “Housing Design: From Concept to Fabrication” has begun in September and will run until the end of October. The learning contents are structured in six topics: Participatory processes, Energy efficiency, Sustainable materials, parametric design, and Digital fabrication.

Learning Spaces

During the Winter semester 2015/16, two new collaborative learning spaces on housing related

topics have started:

"Small is power", space led by KU Leuven that is dedicated to explore the relation between the house and the public realm. OIKONET partners participating in this learning space are Dublin Institute of Technology, School of Architecture La Salle, UCLan, and School of Architecture of Valencia.

"Urban Systems", coordinated by the School of Architecture La Salle, with the collaboration of Chalmers University and the Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona (BCNecologia). It is dedicated to study the superblock in the district of Les Corts as a case study of the compact cities approach.

Participation workshop in Skopje

A workshop that aimed at fostering the participation of architecture students and citizens was led by the Faculty of Architecture from the Ss. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje, from October 15th to 17th. Faculty members from POLIS University, in Albania, and from the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, in Serbia, also participated in this workshop. The outcome of the workshop will be a toolkit and a methodology to take into account the needs of the dwellers in the building and planning processes.

For more information, please visit the Community participation blog.

Meetings

The second general meeting of the OIKONET project was held in Bratislava on September 24th.

The subnetwork Housing Research met for the fourth time in Rotterdam, on June 5th, at the premises of the Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, Erasmus University.

The fourth meeting of the subnetwork Community Participation took place on June 19th at the POLIS University in Tirana. In this meeting the results of the participatory action in Rimini were presented. This was done exhibiting a video produced by two OIKONET partners: Heriscape and Ordine Architetti Rimini.

The fourth meeting of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities took place on May 31st and June 3th at the Department of Architecture of the Brandenburg Technical University, in Cottbus, Germany.

OIKONET on the social web

Are you following OIKONET Facebook pages? If not, join us today! Also, you can find information about the activities of the project members in OIKONET's Google Plus Community. On OIKONET YouTube channel you can find the videos of the project. You can also follow us on Twitter.

Upcoming events

November 20, 2015. The fifth meeting of the group Housing Research will take place in the premises of Faculty of Law of the University of Zagreb.

December 18, 2015. The Community Participation group will have the fifth meeting at the Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, in Skopje.

January 22, 2016. The fifth meeting of the Pedagogical Activities subnetwork will be in Brussels, hosted by the Department of Architecture of KU Leuven.

September 23, 2016. The third OIKONET conference on “Global Dwelling” will take place in Manchester, UK. The conference will be hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, University of Central Lancashire. A call of papers and posters will be announced in the coming weeks.

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A.5 OIKONET Newsletter #05

NEWSLETTER // May 2016

Welcome to the fifth regular newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union, 2013-2016. This project is creating a platform of collaboration to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today’s societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions and pedagogical and research activities bring together various stakeholders and multiple disciplines. Thirty four partners in Europe and around the world participate on the activities of the project, which is approaching its final phase.

The most relevant upcoming events are the third international workshop in Belgrade in June and the third conference on “Global Dwelling”, which will take place in Manchester in September 2016 hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire. The second run of the MOOC “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication” started on May.

The OIKONET Team.

Third OIKONET International Conference: “Global Dwelling: Sustainability-Design-Participation”

The OIKONET conferences on “Global Dwelling” started in 2014 with the first conference at the School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain. A year later, a second conference was held at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology.

The third conference will take place at the Renaissance Hotel, Manchester, UK, on 23 September 2016. A call for papers and posters was issued in December 2015. 44 abstracts have been accepted. Keynote speakers include Iván Tosics, one of the principals of Metropolitan Research Institute (MRI), in Budapest.

Registration is now open. If you need further information, please contact us or visit the conference blog

Third OIKONET International Workshop: “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating liveable cities”

The third OIKONET international workshop “Renewing/Revitalizing: Creating liveable cities” will take place at the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from 6th to 11th of June 2016. This workshop will be dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies will integrate architectural, urban design and urban planning issues to create a multifaceted framework to develop liveable cities.

The workshop will provide a learning environment in which students and faculty members from schools of architecture from different countries in Europe will discuss a variety of approaches to create liveable cities. The learning activities will include lectures, field studies, and practical work in the design studio carried out during the five-day workshop. Before the workshop, during April and May, there are preparatory activities carried out distantly by the participating students assisted by tutors at their institution as well as from other partner schools of the OIKONET network, using OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

You can find more information on the workshop blog or in the Facebook group. If you would like to join the workshop, please contact us.

MOOC “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication”

The MOOC (Massive Online Open Course) "Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication" introduces the design of housing for both expert and novice learners. Through a series of modules, various subjects are combined to produce the design of a housing prototype: participatory processes, sustainability, energy efficiency, parametric design plus a self-study module on digital fabrication. Each module encompasses a number of tasks that lead to explore key ideas in housing design. Students who successfully complete the first three modules will be able to bring their results together to produce a design and / or parametric design for the fourth module. An individual's parametric design can also provide the basis for submission to the course competition. Entries should address the fabrication of their design. For this purpose, a self-study module on “digital fabrication” is included to provide background information on this topic.

A first edition of this MOOC was delivered at the beginning of the academic year. The contents and structure have been reviewed for the second edition that was launched in May 2016. If you would like to enrol, please visit the Canvas website.

Conference Papers, Articles

The paper "Enhancing a Housing Technical Design Studio with a Collaborative On-line Learning Space", by Jim Roche and Leandro Madrazo, was presented at the AACE Global Learn Conference which took place in Limerick, Ireland, April 28-29, 2016.

The article of Josip Panžić “Global Dwelling: Housing Regeneration Strategies” was published in the Croatian Journal of Social Policy, vol. 22, pp.415-419.

Viera Joklova and Henrich Pifko published the article “Innovation in architectural education OIKONET experience” in the Global Journal of Engineering Education (GJEE), Vol.17, No. 3.

Sašo Medved and Boris Vidrih prepared the paper “Evaluating the potential of local urban heat island mitigation by the whitening and greening of the settlement surfaces”.

In June 2016, the paper “Applying a Blended Learning Methodology to the Study of Housing” from Leandro Madrazo, Carla Sentieri and Nadia Charalambous will be presented at the EAAE ARCC International Conference in Lisbon.

OIKONET Reader #2

The second issue of the OIKONET Reader presents a selection of themes on housing proposed by partners involved in the “Housing Research” subnetwork. As the first issue, it illustrates research topics related to contemporary housing policy and practice, which can serve as a guide for the work carried out in the “Pedagogical Activities” and “Community Participation” subnetworks.

The Reader is structured into ten chapters. Chapter 1 discusses urban brownfields regeneration in the UK by reviewing programmes that support and encourage the development of brownfield

sites. Chapter 2 examines the phenomenon of urban heat island and how this can be mitigated by the whitening and greening of urban settlement's outdoor surfaces. Chapter 3 reviews post-conflict regeneration programmes in the historic centre of Nicosia in Cyprus. Chapter 4 discusses neighbourhood regeneration in Oslo, Norway, by critiquing the programme's approach for Inner City East and Groruddalen. Chapter 5 examines regeneration of multi-family buildings in an old mining community in Zagorje ob Savi, Slovenia. Chapter 6 discusses the challenge of privatised housing management across CEE and CIS countries through work conducted by the Housing and Urban Development Studies (IHS), the challenges facing Riga in Latvia are also reviewed. Chapter 7 examines local community responses to urban planning proposals for housing regeneration. Chapter 8 discusses development policies directed at community participation and empowerment, community driven development approaches are used to explain the synergies. Chapter 9 reviews urban planning and the role of participation in housing using the case of Budapest, Hungary. Chapter 10 discusses the concept of housing innovation as an instrument of integrated sustainable urban development; it also examines the requirements for a housing innovation in order to be considered sustainable and affordable. You can access Reader #2 and participate in the discussions in the comments section.

Learning Spaces

In the spring semester 2015/16, four partners are participating in the “Thinking Dwelling” program carrying out activities that are linked to courses at their schools: School of Architecture of Valencia (Spain); Istanbul Technical University (Turkey); Université Grenoble Alpes (France), and University of Puerto Rico. The purpose of the program is engage students and teachers from different courses, levels and schools, in a joint process of reflection about contemporary dwelling. The School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona has produced a publication of the work done in this program at the beginning of this academic year.

Also other open learning spaces (“Introduction to Housing”, “Urban Systems”, "Habitat Regeneration Strategies", “Urban Housing Regeneration”) have been active this semester, involving about a dozen of partners in shared learning activities. You can get more information about OIKONET learning spaces in this report.

Upcoming events

June 6-11, 2016. Third international OIKONET workshop “Renewing / Revitalizing”, Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from 6th to 11th of June 2016. This workshop will be dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. Students from schools that are not OIKONET members can join the workshop with their own funding. If you are interested to participate in the workshop, please contact us at info@oikonet.org.

June 5 and 8, 2016. The sixth and final meeting of the subnetwork “Pedagogical activities” will take place in Belgrade along with the third international workshop.

September 23, 2016. The third OIKONET International Conference will take place at Renaissance Hotel, Manchester, UK, on 23 September 2016. Registration is open, early-bird registration ends on August 31, 2016. More information: conferenceandevents@uclan.ac.uk

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Subnetwork meetings

Sixth meeting of the subnetwork “Housing Research” took place on April 21-22, 2016 at the campus of Riga Technical University in Ķīpsala. The meeting included a study trip to Imanta,

one of Rigas' largest housing estates.

Sixth meeting of the subnetwork “Community Participation” was in Barcelona, March 4, 2016, hosted by the housing cooperative Sostre Cívic.

Fifth meeting of the subnetwork “Pedagogical Activities” was in Brussels, January 22-23, 2016, hosted by the Department of Architecture, KU Leuven (Campus Sint-Lucas). The sixth meeting will be in Belgrade, June 5 and 8, 2016.

Fifth meeting of the subnetwork “Community Participation” was on December 18, 2015 in Skopje, hosted by UKIM - Ss. Cyril and Methodius University.

Fifth meeting of the subnetwork “Housing Research” took place in Zagreb on November 20, 2015. The meeting was hosted by the Institute for Social Policy, University of Zagreb.

Participatory actions

Participatory action in Rimini, Italy: A dissemination campaign is being prepared to disseminate the results of the action through the Ordine degli Architetti. A leaflet has been produced for this purpose.

Participatory action in Bratislava, Slovakia: This action will focus now on the Zemnik area, at the right bank of the river Danube, in May 2016. The city of Bratislava has organized an urban walk to know the views of the different stakeholders involved in the development of the area (citizens, developers, cultural associations).

Participatory action in Skopje, Macedonia: It has been performed with the participation of UKIM from Macedonia, and POLIS from Tirana. The activities are reported in the blog Community Participation.

YouTube Channel

OIKONET YouTube channel is regularly updated with the videos produced in the project. Currently, there have been 2.990 views of the 48 videos produced so far. 24 new videos have been uploaded since September 2015, including the Bratislava conference presentations and lectures in the Thinking Dwelling program.

Exhibitions

An exhibition of posters reflecting the work of OIKONET partners in pedagogy and research was on display during the second OIKONET conference on “Global Dwelling” in Bratislava, in September 2015.

An exhibition of the work produced by students from KU Leuven in the learning space “Small is Power” was in December and January in Leuven.

An exhibition of the work done by students and teachers in the “Thinking Dwelling” program was organized in Barcelona, La Salle, 19-30 October 2015.

An exhibition of the work done by students in the learning space “Urban Systems” was presented in Barcelona, La Salle, 8-15 February 2016.

Posters from OIKONET activities are available as pdf files – if you would like to prepare an exhibition with them, please feel free to send a request to download them.

OIKONET Web Portal

Following the outcomes of a usability test performed by OIKONET partners, the project web portal has been recently enhanced. The changes include the restructuring and simplification of menus, facilitating access to the project outcomes and a tutorial for the OIKONETWORK

graph.

Project Facebook Page

OIKONET Facebook page is a bit more vivid now. Please feel free to publish as a guest information related to the project activities.

A.6 OIKONET Newsletter #06

NEWSLETTER // February 2017

Welcome to the sixth and final newsletter of the OIKONET project, co-financed by the Lifelong Learning Programme of the European Union, 2013-2016. This project has created a collaborative platform to promote the study of contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today's societies (architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social). Participatory actions and pedagogical and research activities have brought together various stakeholders and multiple disciplines. Thirty-four partners in twenty-five countries in Europe and around the world have participated in the project activities.

The most relevant actions in the last period of the project have been the third international conference on “Global Dwelling”, held in Manchester in September 2016, and the third international workshop hosted by the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, in June 2016. The second edition of the OIKONET MOOC “Housing Design” took place in May/June 2016. In the first semester of the academic year 2016/17, the activity around the collaborative learning spaces continued with the second edition of “Thinking Dwelling” and “Urban Systems”. In recent months, partners have been active in the dissemination of the project outcomes in international conferences such as the ENHR in Belfast and the DOCOMOMO in Lisbon.

The project activities carried out with EU support finished on 31th December 2016. Afterwards, the reports of the work were prepared and they will be released to the public in the coming weeks through the project website. The last output of the project is a book which summarizes the work done by the network during the three-years of activity. This book will be available both in printed and on-line versions in May 2017.

Even though the funding period has ended, the project activities continue. During the second semester of 2016/17, there are two learning spaces active in OIKODOMOS Workspaces: a new learning space “Danube Urban and Cultural Studies”, led by the Faculty of Architecture of Slovak Technical University and the sixth edition of “Introduction to Housing”, led by the School of Architecture of Valencia. Lastly, the program of the first OIKONET Postgraduate Workshop to take place in June 2017 at the School of Architecture in Valencia will be announced soon.

The OIKONET Team.

1st OIKONET Postgraduate Workshop

OIKONET starts a series of postgraduate workshops aimed at bringing together researchers interested to explore global dwelling in our contemporary societies from a multidisciplinary and multidimensional perspective. The workshop's aims are:

- to facilitate the knowledge exchange among young researchers, especially PhD students working in fields related to dwelling in contemporary societies.
- to foster the creation of alliances between researchers and their institutions to continue

developing pedagogic and research programs in areas related to the study of contemporary global dwelling.

- to keep developing a framework that brings together pedagogic innovation, housing research and community outreach in order to get a better understanding of today's forms of dwelling and building.

The first workshop will be hosted by the School of Architecture of Valencia and it will take place on June 2017. If you would like to receive more information, please contact us info@oikonet.org.

Over 60 delegates from 27 countries participated in the third OIKONET “Global Dwelling” conference in Manchester

The third OIKONET conference on “Global Dwelling” took place in Manchester, UK, on September 23, 2016, and was hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire. Around 60 delegates from 27 countries, inside and outside Europe, participated in the conference. 24 papers were presented in the parallel sessions which were structured in three themes: 1. Sustainability of housing environments, 2. Innovation in housing design and planning; and 3. Participation in housing design and construction.

A selection of papers will be published in March by WIT Press. A digital version of the proceedings will be soon available at the project website.

59 students and 25 tutors from 17 schools participated in the third OIKONET international workshop “Renewing / Revitalizing”, in Belgrade

The third OIKONET international workshop took place at the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from 6th to 11th June 2016. This workshop was dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. The area of study was Kosančićev Venac, a historical part of the city of Belgrade. It is a heterogeneous, mixed-use area connecting the Sava riverfront with the main pedestrian zone, next to the Kalemegdan fortress. The preparatory stage of the workshop has been done entirely online, using OIKODOMOS Workspaces. In Belgrade, students were organized in ten teams, each one composed of students from different schools to strengthen the cross-cultural and cross-educational exchange. Each team was tutored by teachers from different institutions. The students' proposals have been published in the workshop blog. Posters of the proposals have been on display at the “European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad”, in the historical centre of Belgrade. A reportage about the Belgrade workshop appeared in the Serbian Radio Television.

Second edition of the MOOC “Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication”

The second edition of the OIKONET MOOC (Massive Online Open Course) "Housing Design: from Concept to Fabrication" run in May/June 2016. Following the results of the first 2015 edition of the MOOC, the original program has been reviewed and some of the tasks streamlined to facilitate the work to learners. The learning structure is built around five subjects, each one corresponding to a module of the program: sustainability, energy efficiency, parametric design, digital fabrication, and participatory processes. The five modules led participants from social considerations for design of a simple model of a “Play house” up to the final outputs required for digital fabrication. Over 200 learners were following the MOOC activities in this second edition.

OIKOPEDIA upgrade

OIKOPEDIA -the OIKODOMOS Wikipedia- has been upgraded with 30 new entries written

by OIKONET partners. The topics cover a wide range of issues which have been debated among the members of the Housing Research subnetwork, including: Affordable Housing, Urban Regeneration, Gentrification, Participation, Energy performance, and Sustainability. These entries are available in English, and also in French, Italian, Russian, Slovak, Spanish, and Turkish.

Learning spaces

27 international bachelor and master students in architecture will participate in the OIKONET elective at the Faculty of Architecture KU Leuven this spring semester. In previous years this elective addressed topics as “Threshold Matters” and “Small is Power”. On this occasion the topic will be “A Moment of Architecture” and it is intended to be a designerly reflection about the interrelationships between private and public realms. Teachers and researchers from UCLan- Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, UK and from the Department of Architecture, Design and Media Technology, University of Aalborg, Denmark, will participate in the elective course. You can follow the activities of the elective course in this Facebook group.

“Danube Urban and Cultural Studies” is a new learning space led by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University which will run during the spring semester 2016/2017. Three new partners will be involved in this learning space: Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary; Technische Universität Wien, Austria; and Donau Universität Krems, Austria. The purpose of the learning activities will be to identify, analyse and apply strategies to strengthen the Danube regional cultural identity by fostering transnational cultural ties between the settlements along the river.

The second edition of the learning space “Urban Systems” was carried out in conjunction with “Research seminar on contemporary housing” conducted at the School of Architecture La Salle. As in the previous edition, the activities focused on understanding cities from a systems perspective. In this edition, the case studies were four urban axes in the city of Barcelona which concentrate the city’s activities around them. At the end of the seminar, students presented their proposals in a public hearing at Can Felipa, a community centre in the area of Poble Nou. Representatives of neighbours’ associations and urban activists attended the presentations and participated in a debate with students and teachers. The work done in the seminar was discussed in a colloquium broadcasted by Radio Ciutat Vella, a local radio station. An exhibition of the students’ works will be on display in the Can Felipa community centre during April 2017.

On September 14th 2016 started the second edition of the “Thinking Dwelling” program at the School of Architecture La Salle. In the week from 19th to 23th September, students and teachers participated in a joint reflection about dwelling in our contemporary societies. Five presentations by faculty members followed by a discussion took place in the exhibition space especially organized for this event. The recorded presentations are accessible at the OIKONET YouTube channel.

Conference Papers, Articles

Carla Sentieri has presented a paper to the conference “JIDA’16. IV Jornadas sobre innovación docente en arquitectura” which took place in Valencia, Spain, on 20th and 21st October, 2016. The paper titled “The integration of a collaborative platform with the design studio: a reflection about the participation in the OIKONET project” summarizes the experience of the participation of the School of Architecture of Valencia in OIKONET, in particular, the work done in the learning space “Introduction to Housing”, which the school is leading since the academic year 2013/14.

Sandra Marques Pereira, from the University Institute of Lisbon, and Jim Roche, from the

Dublin School of Architecture, DIT, have presented the paper “Across Disciplinary and National Borders: a pedagogical tool for re-use” at the 14th International Docomomo Conference that took place in, Lisbon, Portugal, from 6th to 9th September 2016. The paper contains a reflection on the work done at the first international OIKONET workshop, dedicated to analysing formal and informal settlements in Lisbon.

Leandro Madrazo and Angel Martin presented the paper “Developing strategies for sustainable neighbourhoods” at the conference of the European Network for Housing Research conference in Belfast. The paper summarizes the work done in the learning space “Housing Systems” which was dedicated to analyse the superblock model implemented in some areas of the city of Barcelona to improve the city’s liveability.

Upcoming events

April, 2017. Publication of the papers presented at the third OIKONET conference in the book “Global Dwelling. Approaches to Sustainability, Design and Participation”, published by WIT Press.

May, 2017. Publication of the book summarizing the activities of the network. The book will be available in printed and on-line forms. If you are interested to get an exemplar, please contact us info@oikonet.org.

May, 2017. Final reports of the activities done in the three-year project in the three subnetworks – Housing Research, Pedagogical Activities and Community Participation- to be published in the project website.

June, 2017. First OIKONET Postgraduate Workshop will take place at the School of Architecture in Valencia. If you would like to participate, please contact us info@oikonet.org.

Participatory actions

Participatory action in Rimini, Italy: The Chamber of Architects of Rimini and Heriscape organized a one-day conference in Rimini, September 27, 2016, on the theme “Housing sociale e partecipazione di comunità”. With this opportunity, the outcomes of the participatory action implemented by the two OIKONET partners in Rimini were discussed. The meeting was recorded and it is available in YouTube.

Exhibitions

An exhibition with the contributions of participants in the “Thinking Dwelling” program has been on display at La Salle School of Architecture, at the start of the second edition of this program, from 14th to 30th September 2016.

YouTube Channel

OIKONET YouTube channel is regularly updated with the videos produced in the project. Currently, there have been 3.730 views of the 53 videos produced so far. The last uploads are the presentations of the second edition of the “Thinking Dwelling” program at La Salle School of Architecture.

Project Facebook Page

In OIKONET Facebook page you can have more lively information of the various activities carried out during the project.

Forward to a friend

Do you know someone who might be interested in receiving the OIKONET Newsletter?. You

can ask for a subscription at info@oikonet.org

A.7 First International Conference Global Dwelling

GLOBAL DWELLING | 25-26 September 2014

School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona

This conference will address the global dimension of contemporary housing as manifested in the demands for citizens' participation, social inclusiveness, adaptability and sustainability of the built environment and fostering a sense of belonging. Even though the specific answers to these demands differ in each society the underlying forces that support them have a global dimension. An appropriate answer will not derive exclusively from the solutions that professionals – architects, urban planners – can provide based on their established body of knowledge. Rather, it is necessary to confront those demands in an open manner, investigating the nature of the problem in collaboration with all stakeholders involved, in order to find the appropriate answer to the challenges that dwelling raises today.

Therefore, the conference will bring together representatives of academic institutions, research organizations, community groups and local authorities, with the purpose to fostering a common view of what housing means today, at a global scale.

OPEN CALL FOR POSTERS: A poster exhibition is included in the programme. If you would like to present a poster, please contact us. The deadline to receive the final version of the paper (in A0 format) is July 31, 2014.

Please see the **CONFERENCE PROGRAM** and **POSTER**

Keynote speakers

Claire Lévy-Vroelant is a professor of Sociology at the University of Paris 8 Saint-Denis, France, and researcher at the Centre de Recherche sur l'Habitat. Since 2006, she has been guest professor at the University of Vienna. Her work intersects the fields of Urbanism, Migration, Housing, and more recently Memory Studies to deal with questions concerning housing policies and social issues in a globalizing context. Currently, her research work focuses on the meanings of hospitality and collective memory. After having been a member of the coordination committee of the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) from 2006 to 2012, she is now co-chairing a permanent ENHR working group on "Social housing and globalization". She is member of several international editorial boards and director of the collection "Habitat and Sociétés", L'Harmattan, Paris. Recently, she has co-authored the book "Lieux de mémoire de l'immigration", a study about the living places of immigrants in Paris.

Ekim Tan is the founder of the city design and research network "The Responsive City". She is an experienced researcher and designer of international urban design projects. She has worked with Rotterdam-based offices Urban Affairs and De Urbanisten, as well as with Dutch municipalities and urban design offices in projects such as creating city vision 2035 for Rotterdam, Veenkolonien in Groningen, Homeruskwartier and Almere. She has been regularly teaching and lecturing worldwide. Ekim graduated as an architect at Middle East Technical University with the Archiprix Award in 1999, and got her second degree in Urbanism at TU Delft, with distinctions, in 2005. Currently, she is completing her PhD studies at TU Delft and the International New Towns Institute.

The conference program includes 19 presentations by representatives coming from 25 countries worldwide which will address the following topics: changing meanings of home, housing policies, energy efficiency in housing, social sustainability, affordable housing, community

participation, housing design education, sustainable housing, and urban renewal.

INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANTS:

The conference will take place at the premises of the School of Architecture La Salle, Quatre Camins 2, Barcelona, Spain. The participation in this conference is free of charge. If you are interested to attend, please write to info@oikonet.org. The papers presented at the conference will be collected in a digital publication which will be available in the project website.

A.8 Second International Conference Global Dwelling

Second International Conference

GLOBAL DWELLING Housing regeneration strategies

Bratislava, 25 September 2015

The second OIKONET conference on the topic Global Dwelling will focus on regeneration strategies as mechanisms that are applied to improve the existing living conditions in urban areas around the world. Nowadays, various local and global factors cause the appearance of disadvantaged communities and declining urban areas worldwide. Instead of offering universal solutions, contemporary integrated interventions are intended to tackle specific problems by encompassing social, economic and urban dimensions. By building on existing local forces – involving all stakeholders and the local community in the process of finding solutions–, urban areas can unleash their endogenous regeneration potential. Even though being deeply influenced by local conditions, this process acquires a global dimension when certain mechanisms and policies – such as planned gentrification and social mix – are reproduced at multiple locations and cultures.

The conference will discuss the implications of such integrated approaches based on the design and implementation of strategies for the regeneration of communities – at a social, economic and environmental level. We invite researchers, lecturers, design studio instructors, policy makers, practitioners and community leaders, involved in the research, design and implementation of housing regeneration strategies, to submit original papers addressing the following issues:

- What are the consequences – for architecture and urban planning education – of designing regeneration strategies instead of designing housing developments?
- How are the visions and goals in a community renewal process, collectively defined?
- Which urban regeneration strategies are needed to achieve a sustainable urban development (at the cultural, economic, social and environmental level)?
- Are there any alternatives to gentrification as driver of urban regeneration?
- How current learning and teaching practices in architecture and urban planning should change to support community development?
- Which methods and techniques are needed to unleash the endogenous regeneration potentials of communities?
- How can community participation be integrated alongside professional expertise to define the objectives of an urban renewal process?
- How can the global and local dimensions involved in a regeneration process become intertwined?

We welcome critical presentations of case studies addressing regeneration practices all over the world. We particularly encourage the submission of works that explore methodologies for creating links between community-based research and innovative learning practices which bring together professionals and non-professionals in the process of renewing the urban

habitat.

Call for papers

We invite the submission of abstracts (maximum 2 pages) that will be evaluated by the Scientific Committee members. Up to 12 abstracts will be selected to present a paper that will be published in the proceedings and presented at the conference.

Poster session

Abstracts that are not accepted will have the opportunity to be presented in the poster session. We specially encourage PhD students and researchers to present a poster about their in-progress work. A template will be provided upon request to prepare an A0 poster.

Deadlines

Please be aware of the following deadlines:

- ABSTRACT SUBMISSION: 15 April 2015
- NOTIFICATION OF ACCEPTANCE: 30 April 2015
- PAPER SUBMISSION: 15 June 2015
- DEADLINE FOR REGISTRATION: 4 September 2015
- POSTER SUBMISSION: 15 July 2015

For more information please visit the conference blog or contact us at info@oikonet.org

Keynote speakers

Becky Tunstall is the Joseph Rowntree Professor of Housing Policy and Director of the Centre for Housing Policy at the University of York. The Centre carries out a wide range of projects on current housing issues for government departments, housing associations, third sector organisations and academic research councils. Becky's current major studies include Co-Motion, a study of the built environment, mobility and wellbeing for older people, a study of the interaction between housing circumstances and poverty over time, a project on barriers to employment for women housing association tenants in London, and an investigation of the long-term impact of housing quality on health in Scotland. She teaches on social enterprise and on global urban social policy. For many years she was the course leader for the MSc/Dip Housing at the London School of Economics, where she was a member of the Centre for the Analysis of Social Exclusion. She has also worked at the Brookings Institution in Washington DC. She has studied politics, urban design and fine art.

Aseem Inam Ph.D. is Director of TRULAB: Laboratory for Designing Urban Transformation and Associate Professor of Urbanism at Parsons The New School for Design in New York City. He is also Fellow at the Center for Ethics and Transformative Values at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Affiliate of the Civitas Atheneum Laboratory at the Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm. He is the author of two books, "Designing Urban Transformation" and "Planning for the Unplanned: Recovering from Crises in Megacities", as well as of several journal articles and book chapters, including in the recent book "Companion to Urban Design". He has also practiced as an architect, urban designer and planner in Brazil, Canada, France, Greece, Haiti, India and the United States. His teaching, research and practice have received awards from the American Planning Association, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, the SOM Foundation, and the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development.

A.9 Third International Conference Global Dwelling

Third International Conference

GLOBAL DWELLING Sustainability - Design – Participation

Manchester, 23 September 2016

The third OIKONET conference on ‘Global Dwelling’ will be hosted by the Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, School of Art, Design and Fashion, University of Central Lancashire. OIKONET is a European project co-funded by the Executive Agency of Education, Audiovisual and Culture (EACEA) with the purpose of studying contemporary housing from a multidisciplinary and global perspective by encompassing the multiple dimensions which condition the forms of dwelling in today’s societies: architectural, urban, environmental, economic, cultural and social.

The first OIKONET conference was organized by La Salle School of Architecture in Barcelona, Spain, in September 2014; the second one by the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, in September 2015. This third conference will showcase the results obtained in the three years of activity of OIKONET intertwining research, pedagogy and community participation around the topic ‘Global Dwelling’. During this period OIKONET partners have been involved in the design and implementation of pedagogic and research activities which have brought together schools of architecture and planning, research groups, professional organizations and local administrations. This is reflected in the collaborative learning spaces and workshops, community-based projects and participatory actions carried out with the participation of architecture students, lecturers, researchers and citizens.

The conference program will be structure in three themes:

1. Sustainability of housing environments. The problem of sustainability has been widely recognised as a priority by governments, civil society and businesses across the world. The built environment is a key component of a sustainable development, and the need for sustainable housing environments and communities cannot be overemphasised given the increasing demand for waste minimisation, sustainable transport and renewable energy.
2. Innovation in housing design and planning. Processes of housing design and production are increasingly more global due to the networking of knowledge, professionals and organizations. Innovative housing design solutions at the dwelling and neighbourhood levels are needed to respond to societal changes such as an ageing population, new living arrangements and lifestyles, and affordability.
3. Participation in housing design and construction. During the last few decades, achieving the participation of citizens in the processes of housing design and construction has been an objective for professionals and policy makers in many countries around the world. Innovative pedagogical methods are required for students to acquire the skills they need to interact with non-professionals in participatory processes.

Call for papers

We invite researchers, lecturers, design studio instructors, policy makers, practitioners and community leaders involved in the research, teaching, design and provision of housing, from unit/building to urban and regional scales, to submit original papers and posters addressing one of the conference three themes and considering, among others, the following questions:

1. What are the challenges facing sustainable housing environments and communities, globally?
2. What is the future of public rental housing and its affordability?
3. What are the alternatives to gentrification as driver of urban regeneration?

4. What are the lessons learned from mass housing renovations?
5. What are the standards that should shape future housing?
6. What should be changed in current architectural programmes to train architects how to interact with residents during the procurement processes of new housing?
7. How can housing communities be mobilised and strategic alliances established in order to foster innovation in housing?
8. How can future participatory processes learn from past experiences?
9. What does ‘learning to dwell’ mean in our contemporary world?

The abstracts (maximum 350 words) will be evaluated by the Scientific Committee. Authors with accepted abstract will be required to submit a full paper following the deadlines below.

Poster session

We also invite submission of posters from non-academic organisations such as Housing Associations and Housing Developers to showcase housing projects, initiatives and innovations. Additionally, abstracts that are not accepted for paper presentation will have the opportunity to be presented at the poster session. We encourage PhD students to submit a paper or a poster about their research work. Templates will be provided for the paper and poster.

Deadlines

Please be aware of the following deadlines:

- ABSTRACT SUBMISSION 15 February 2016
- NOTIFICATION OF ACCEPTANCE 29 February 2016
- PAPER SUBMISSION 31 May 2016
- POSTER SUBMISSION 31 July 2016
- DEADLINE FOR REGISTRATION 1 August 2016

For more information please visit the conference blog or contact us at ConferenceAndEvents@uclan.ac.uk

Keynote speakers

Becky Tunstall is the Joseph Rowntree Professor of Housing Policy and Director of the Centre for Housing Policy at the University of York. The Centre carries out a wide range of projects on current housing issues for government departments, housing associations, third sector organisations and academic research councils (see www.york.ac.uk/chp). Becky's current major studies include Co-Motion, a study of the built environment, mobility and wellbeing for older people, a study of the interaction between housing circumstances and poverty over time, a project on barriers to employment for women housing association tenants in London, and an investigation of the long-term impact of housing quality on health in Scotland. She teaches on social enterprise and on global urban social policy. For many years she was the course leader for the MSc/Dip Housing at the London School of Economics, where she was a member of the Centre for the Analysis of Social Exclusion. She has also worked at the Brookings Institution in Washington DC. She has studied politics, urban design and fine art.

Iván Tosics is one of the principals of Metropolitan Research Institute (MRI), Budapest. He is mathematician and sociologist (PhD) with long experience in urban development, strategic planning, and housing policy and EU regional policy issues. Since 2011 he is one of the four Thematic Pole Managers of the URBACT programme. He teaches at the University of Pécs, Department of Political Studies, Doctoral School. He is vice chair of the European Network of Housing Research (ENHR), executive committee member of the European Urban Research

Association (EURA). Iván is the Policy Editor of the journal 'Urban Research and Practice'. He was part of the consortium performing for DG Regio the study on the use of housing interventions from European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) resources. He participated in the work lead by AEIDL 'Good practice in urban development: Projects and approaches supported by the European Regional Development Fund during the 2007-2013 programming period', prepared for DG Regio. He was invited as expert to the European Parliament public hearing on 'The place of Europe's towns and cities in Cohesion policy'. He was working for DG Regio in the Cities of Tomorrow programme, preparing an issue paper on 'Governance challenges and models for the cities of tomorrow'. He was one of the organizers of the high-level conference on Demographic changes during the Hungarian EU Presidency. He was Lead Expert of two URBACT programmes. Iván represented for many years the Municipality of Budapest in EURO CITIES, as chair of the Economic Development Forum in 2007-2008 and as member of the Executive Committee in 2009-2010. He participated in the preparation of the Rehabilitation Strategy of Budapest, and he was the leader of a consortium working on the medium and long term Urban Development Strategy of Budapest.

OIKONET GLOBAL DWELLING CONFERENCES SERIES

The first OIKONET conference was organized by La Salle School of Architecture in September 2014; the second one at the Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, in September 2015. The third conference, organized by the University of Central Lancashire (UCLAN), will take place in Manchester, in September 2016.

PROGRAM

The conference program will have three sessions one for each theme during the morning and afternoon, on Friday September 23, 2016. The conference opens at 9:00 am and ends at 6:30 pm. A poster session will open at the Manchester School of Architecture on Thursday 25, at 6 pm.

VENUE

The conference will take place at the Manchester School of Architecture, Chatham Building, Cavendish Street, Manchester, UK.

REGISTRATION

Registration will open on 1 June 2016. Conference fee includes conference pack, lunches, refreshments, and conference dinner on Friday 23 September 2016. Standard registration: Early (before 1 August 2016): £300 After 1 August 2016: £350 Student registration: Early (before 1 August 2016): £75 After 1 August 2016: £100

PUBLICATION OF PAPERS

Papers will be peer reviewed by at least two members of the Scientific Committee. Accepted papers will be published in Volume Number 173 in WIT Transactions on The Built Environment. WIT Press will promote, market and distribute the Conference Proceedings internationally.

APPENDIX B. OIKONET Newsletter Statistics

The following table provides an overview of the opening and clicking ratio of the already published issues of the OIKONET newsletter.

Table B.1. Subscribers, opening and clicking rates of the OIKONET newsletter

Issue	Recipients	Opened	Clicked
#01 – March 2014	70	58.0%	13.0%
Special issue – June 2014	70	70.0%	18.6%
#02 – September 2014	193	49.7%	15.7%
Special issue – March 2015	192	62.5%	9.9%
#03 – April 2015	207	51.7%	7.3%
#04 – October 2015	265	43.2%	7.3%
Special issue – December 2015	262	44.4%	5.8%
Special issue – February 2016	263	42.9%	7.3%
#05 – May 2016	312	40.8%	6.4%
#06 – February 2017	363	32.9%	3.2%
List average	-	49.5%	9,3%
Industry average (education)	-	16.1%	1.9%

Table B.2. Subscribers and openings of the OIKONET newsletter .

The reading of the newsletter was evaluated in the frame of WP6 – respondents were members of project partner organisations. Following information is copied from the D6.4 report:

From the answers to the questions about the newsletter in the online survey, it emerged that 10 respondents (40%) fully read the received newsletters, 12 (48%) read them partially, while 3 respondents (12%) did not read the newsletters at all. 7 respondents (28%) forwarded at least one issue of the newsletter to a colleague. One respondent found the newsletters helpful to have a brief overview of the activities that are part of the programme. Other partners suggested to better design the material and to have more real life stories and more illustrative materials to present and explain the project activities.